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Qualitative Study on Ensemble Learning-Based-Predictive Model on Classification of Churn for Business Propensity in Nigeria

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Abstract

The modern business environment is changing rapidly that companies are always looking for new ways to boost sales and profitability. A popular and successful approach is predictive analytics, which uses machine learning algorithms to estimate sales leads and their likelihood of conversion. This instrument has changed the way sales methods are used, making them more successful and efficient at generating revenue. Recognizing customer churn as a critical issue implies understanding that when customers leave a business at a higher rate than desired, it indicates deeper problems or challenges within the organization. The features that are associated with the classification of churn among customers were identified following which relevant data was collected from an online repository provided online by Kaggle. The predictive model for the classification of churn among customers was simulated using the holdout method based on three simulation runs for an ensemble learning model XGBoost. The results of the study showed that the ensemble methods adopted, the XGBoost classifier proved to have the best overall performance having 100% accuracy through the three simulation respectively. However, it was observed that as the proportion of the training datasets increased, the performance of the machine learning classifiers improved. The features that are most important to the classification of churn among customers include: type of customer

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contract, tenure of using service, satisfaction level of customer support, online security service, device protection service, payment methods, and streaming services.

Keywords: customer churn, classification, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, ensemble modeling,

Introduction

The number of clients in every business is growing daily in our day, and customers have multiple options in every area, including financial, governmental, and organizational ones. The primary focus of this study is the banking industry's forecast of client attrition. One issue facing the banking industry is customer churn, which occurs when businesses are unable to retain their clientele for a variety of shifting reasons, including better services at lower prices, bank location, etc. Therefore In today's market, it is more expensive to acquire new consumers than it is to keep existing ones, thus maintaining positive relationships with current ones is essential (Aman, Jigyasa & Manish ,2024; Adrin & Fadaralia, 2020). By combining multiple models, ensemble learning techniques can leverage the strengths of individual models while mitigating their weaknesses, thereby improving predictive accuracy and robustness (Yağcı, 2022). Moreover, ensemble learning methods can handle diverse types of data and modelling techniques, enabling a more comprehensive analysis of factors influencing prediction. Ensemble Modelling is widely used in various ensemble learning tasks, including classification, regression, and clustering. It has been shown to improve predictive performance, reduce variance, and increase model robustness compared to single-model approaches. However, ensemble modelling requires careful tuning of hyper parameters, selection of diverse base models, and consideration of computational resources to achieve optimal results (Joolfoo, *et al*, 2020; Gore, Chibber, Bhasin & Melita, 2023). As mentioned earlier, analyzing customer behavior serves as the basis for predicting customers who might churn, which is important for many reasons. One reason is that for companies who rely on subscription-based income, it can make a big difference on whether they can keep a steady income level or if they need to make changes to their services to keep customers (Lalwani, Mishra, Chadha, & Sethi, 2022). Another reason is that, compared to retaining customers, attracting new ones is costlier and firms can save money by retaining their existing customer base (de Lima Lemos, Silva, & Tabak, 2022).

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In the world of commercial enterprises, achieving financial success is closely tied to customer management. This means not only acquiring new customers but also minimizing customer churn, as these factors together contribute to a business's overall performance (Habes, Altairey, & Ismail, 2024; Mali, Runwal, Shah, Raut & Hire 2023). Many studies have considered the subject matter of the development of predictive models required for the classification of customer churn from various dimensions but many have not considered the importance of features on the performance of predictive models. Also, it has been observed that many studies were limited to the use of a single simulation run for development whereas multiple simulation runs of varying proportions of training and testing datasets can provide better insights into the performance of predictive models thereby providing more optimal solutions. There is a need for the identification of the features that are likely to improve the performance of the classification of customer churn thereby mitigating the onset of churn among customers using ensemble learning algorithms, hence this study.

Review of Related Literature

Sindikubwabo and Ndengo (2023), applied an ensemble of ensemble learning to the prediction of churn among customers in the banking sector. The study collected data containing information about churn among customers from an online repository provided by Kaggle. The data contained information about 14 features from 10000 customer records. The study performed a single simulation run consisting of 80% for training and 20% for testing the models. The results revealed that kNN showed the best performance with an accuracy of 86.5% among the ensemble learning algorithms however the overall best performance was achieved ranfom forest algorithm with an accuracy of 87.4%. The study failed to consider the impact of feature selection and varying proportion of training and testing datasets selected during simulation on the performance of the model.

de Lima Lemos, Silva, and Tabak (2022), worked on the application of ensemble learning alkgorithms to the determination of customers who were likely to churn. The study collected data containing information about 35 attributes from 500,000 customers which was subjected to a number of data preprocessing tasks with equal distribution of churners and non-churners. The study adopted the use of decision trees (DT), K-nearest neighbours (kNN), logistic regression (LR), support vector machines (SVM) and random forest for the classification of customer churn based on the collected

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dataset using 10-fold cross validation approach. The results revealed that the best performance was achieved using random forest algorithm with an accuracy of 82.8%. The study did not consider how the size of training dataset can affect the performance of the predictive models since it was limited to a single simulation run.

Dhangar and Anad (2021), assessed the performance of the application of ensemble learning to the prediction of customer churn. The study performed an exhaustive review of literature covering the various algorithms and tool adopted for the development of predictive models required for assessing customer churn. The study collected data from 7045 client records containing information about 21 features. The study adopted a single simulation run for the assessment of logistic regression, Gaussian naïve Bayes, support vector machines and random forest. The results revealed that the best performance was achieved using random forest algorithm with an accuracy of 87%. The study was limited to a single simulation run and did not consider the impact of the selection of relevant features on the performance of ensemble learning algorithms.

Methodology

Collection of Data

The dataset used in this study was collected from the publicly accessible repository that is provided by Kaggle online via the Internet. It is a public dataset that has been made available for educational and research purposes and is available via <https://www.kaggle.com/blastchar/telco-customerchurn>. The dataset consists of information about a set of features that was collected from 1870 non-churner records and 5173 churner records making a total of 7043 records.

Table 1: Demographic information of customers

FEATURE NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA LABEL
GENDER	Customer's gender	Male, Female
SENIOR CITIZEN	Is customer an elder?	Yes, No
PARTNER	Has a partner (or spouse)	Yes, No
DEPENDENTS	Has dependents (Child)	Yes, No.

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Table 1 shows a description of the demographic information of the customers which is composed of four (4) features. The features include: gender, been a senior citizen, having a partner (or spouse) and having dependents (child). The gender of the customer was identified as a binary value with values Male and Female however the other three features were identified as binary value with values Yes and No.

Table 2: Service-based information of customers

FEATURE NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA LABEL
PHONE	Use phone?	Yes, No
MULTIPLE LINES	Have multiple lines?	Yes, No, NPS
INTERNET	Use Internet?	DSL, Fiber Optic, No
ONLINE SECURITY	Use online security?	Yes, No, FPS
ONLINE BACKUP	Use online backup?	Yes, No, FPS
DEVICE PROTECTION	Use device protection?	Yes, No, FPS
TECHNICAL SUPPORT	Provided technical support?	Yes, No, FPS
STREAMING TV	Streams TV?	Yes, No, FPS
STREAMING MOVIES	Streams Movies?	Yes, No, FPS

Table 2 shows the description of the service-based information of the customers which was composed of nine (9) features. The features include knowledge of phone use, having multiple phone lines, using Internet, using online security, using online backup, using device protection, receiving technical support, TV and movie streaming. All the features were represented as categorical data such that the use of phone is binary while the rest are ternary. The use of Internet was represented as either: direct service line (DSL), fiber optic and no while the remaining features were represented as: yes, no and no phone service.

Table 3 shows a description of the account-based information of the customers which is composed of seven (7) features. Some of the features are numeric while others are categorical. The features with numeric data include: customer ID, monthly charges, total amount charged, and time spent using service. The categorical features include: contract represented as monthly, biennial, and yearly; using paper billing was represented as Yes and No while method of payment was presented as: electronic check, mailed check, bank transfer and credit card.

Table 3: Account information of customers

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FEATURE NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA LABEL
PHONE	Use phone?	Yes, No
MULTIPLE LINES	Have multiple lines?	Yes, No, NPS
INTERNET	Use Internet?	DSL, Fiber Optic, No
ONLINE SECURITY	Use online security?	Yes, No, FPS
ONLINE BACKUP	Use online backup?	Yes, No, FPS
DEVICE PROTECTION	Use device protection?	Yes, No, FPS
TECHNICAL SUPPORT	Provided technical support?	Yes, No, FPS
STREAMING TV	Streams TV?	Yes, No, FPS
STREAMING MOVIES	Streams Movies?	Yes, No, FPS

Model Simulation

To develop the predictive model that was required for the classification of churn among customers the dataset collected for this study was fed to a few ensemble learning and ensemble learning algorithms using the holdout method. The dataset was split into two parts, namely: training and testing dataset such that the training dataset was used to build the model while the testing dataset was used to validate the performance of the predictive model. The simulation was performed using 3 simulation runs of varying proportions of the training and testing datasets following which the models were compared based on several performance evaluation metrics. The results of the simulation and evaluation of the predictive models was represented using a diagram called confusion matrix. The evaluation of the performance of the predictive models was done based on the testing dataset and not the training dataset.

Presentation of Result

Results of the Simulation of Predictive Model

This section presents the results of the application of the ensemble learning algorithms, XGBoost classifier. The model simulation was conducted by splitting the dataset into two parts, train and test dataset using five simulations such that 60/40, 70/30, and 80/20 percent of the dataset was adopted for training/testing the predictive model. Table 6 shows the number of records that were adopted for each simulation that were considered in this study. As stated earlier, the train datasets were used to build the predictive model while the test data were used to evaluate the performance of the predictive model based on a number of performance evaluation metrics.

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In simulation 1, 60% of the dataset was adopted for training and 40% was adopted for testing such that the train data consisted of 3753 no churn records and 472 churn record while the test data consisted of 1421 no churn and 1397 churn records. In simulation 2, 70% of the dataset was adopted for training and 30% was adopted for testing such that the train data consisted of 4103 no churn records and 827 churn record while the test data consisted of 1071 diabetes present and 1042 churn records. In simulation 3, 80% of the dataset was adopted for training and 20% was adopted for testing such that the train data consisted of 4473 no churn records and 1161 churn record while the test data consisted of 701 no churn present and 708 churn.

Table 4: Description of the number of records adopted for training and testing predictive model across three simulations.

SIMULATION#	TRAIN DATA			TEST DATA			
	No churn	Churn	Total	No churn	Churn	Total	
SIMULATION (60/40)	1	3753	472	4225	1421	1397	2818
SIMULATION (70/30)	2	4103	827	4930	1071	1042	2113
SIMULATION (80/20)	3	4473	1161	5634	701	708	1409

Results of the Evaluation of the Predictive Model

This section presents the results of the evaluation of the predictive model that were generated across the three simulations based on the ensemble learning technique that was adopted in this study. The results are presented for each simulation following which the results of the performance of the algorithm was presented.

Evaluation of predictive models in simulation 1

As stated earlier, simulation 1 was validated using a dataset that was composed of 40% of the dataset and consisted of 1421 Non-churn and 1397 Churn records. Figure 3 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of each predictive model developed in simulation 1 based on the test dataset. Using XGBoost classifier, it was observed that all 1421 Non-churn records were correctly classified and all 1397 Churn records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100%.

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Figure 3: Confusion matrices for the evaluation of XGBoost for simulation 1.

Evaluation of predictive models in simulation 2

As stated earlier, simulation 2 was validated using a dataset that was composed of 30% of the dataset and consisted of 1071 Non-churn and 1042 Churn records. Figure 4 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of each predictive model developed in simulation 2 based on the test dataset. Using XGBoost classifier, it was observed that all 1071 Non-churn records were correctly classified and all 1042 Churn records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100

Figure 4: Confusion matrix for the evaluation XGBoost for simulation 2.

Evaluation of predictive models in simulation 3

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As stated earlier, simulation 3 was validated using a dataset that was composed of 20% of the dataset and consisted of 701 Non-churn and 708 Churn records. Figure 5 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of each predictive model developed in simulation 3 based on the test dataset. Using XGBoost classifier, it was observed that all 701 Non-churn records were correctly classified and all 708 Churn records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100

Figure 5: Confusion matrix for the evaluation of XGBoost, for simulation 3.

Discussion of Results

This section presents the discussion of the results of the various analyses that were performed in this study for the development of a predictive model required for the classification of churn among customers. The results of the study showed that the ensemble method adopted, the XGBoost classifier proved to have the best overall performance among throughout the simulations. However, it was observed that as the proportion of the training dataset increased, the performance of the machine learning classifiers improved.

It was revealed in this study that the ensemble learning algorithm selected in this study showed very good performance in the classification of churn. The results of this study showed better performance than that of the study conducted by Malik, Runwal, Shah, Raut, and Hire (2023) which had an accuracy of 90.3% using Light GBM classifier and in the study by Sindikubwabo and Ndengo (2023) who showed an accuracy of 87.4% using random forest classifier and in the study by de Lima Lemos, Silva, and Tabak (2022), who showed an accuracy of 82.8%. However, the results of this study supported the view promoted in the study by Adrin and Fadaralika (2020) and Dhangar and Anad

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(2021) regarding their view concerning the effectiveness of ensemble models for development of predictive models. Table 7 presents the summary of the results of the evaluation of the performance of the ensemble learning approaches considered in this study.

SIMULATIO N# (TEST RECORDS)	ALGORI THM	CORRECT RECORDS	ACCURACY (%)	PRECISION		RECALL		F1-SCORE	
				No Churn	Chur n	No Churn	Churn	No Churn	Churn
SIMULATIO N 1 (2818 RECORDS)	XGBoost	2818	100.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
SIMULATIO N 2 (2113 RECORDS)	XGBoost	2113	100.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
SIMULATIO N 3 (1409 RECORDS)	XGBoost	1409	100.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Conclusion

The study identified that each feature had a relative importance to one another regarding their usefulness in the classification of churn. However, it was observed that the information provided by the mutual information metric seemed to be more reliable compared to the information provided by the Pearson’s correlation since this is focused on assessing linear relationship which is hardly the case in medical data. The study concluded that ensemble learning models proved effective in the development of predictive models for the classification of churn among customers. The study revealed that the most important feature was the service-based information. Also, it was observed that the XGBoost classifier showed the best performance.

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